

CIRAN

D7.1

Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation

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Executive Summary

This Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation (PDE) will guide the implementation of Task 7.1 “Communication and Outreach” of the CIRAN project. The main goals of the task are:

1. Dissemination: informing stakeholders about the project outputs and results, and seeking synergies with related projects.
2. Exploitation: ensuring effective dissemination of CIRAN achievements and supporting the uptake of results by policymakers, regulators, communities, and the general public.
3. Communication: enabling the transfer of science-based information in dialogues and the co-creation processes with citizens from communities located in selected environmentally protected areas, including their vicinity, and, in line with these developments, providing information and raising awareness about the project to a broader audience, including the media, and the general public.

The main objective of the CIRAN project is to develop, test, and validate processes to arrive at systemic policymaking, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs). The implementation of the Plan will be led by the Task Leader (LPRC), supported by the Work Package (WP) 7 Leader (SGU) and the coordinating organisation (INTRAW), and will be executed in collaboration with all consortium members, thus ensuring the maximum impact and wider dissemination of results. The primary target group of CIRAN dissemination and communication are policymakers and implementers engaged in minerals resources management, nature conservation, and land-use planning from national, regional, and local authorities of EU Member States, and who are indispensable to enable the domestic extraction of CRMs and attain the EU Green Deal climate ambition. The wider CIRAN communication and engagement strategy is primarily aimed towards engaging in a two-way discussion with the stakeholders, including the citizens in selected communities. The project will use a combination of various media channels to communicate effectively, focusing on online tools and educational materials.

The Plan defines communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities with corresponding timing recommendations, responsibilities, target audiences, key messages, and communication tools. The aim is to ensure that the project knowledge and findings will reach and be taken up by the stakeholders. The Plan will be monitored, adapted, and updated during the project implementation with any relevant aspects. The exploitation plan focuses particularly on the plans and assessments made to foster the exploitable outputs generated. It is expected that the most relevant uptake of CIRAN’s results will take place at the policy design and implementation levels, fostered by the CIRAN Forum. This document constitutes the first deliverable of WP7, and, thus, will be monitored, adapted, and updated during the implementation of the project with any new information and results that could emerge.

Links with Other Project Activities

CIRAN’s methodology consists of seven work packages (WPs), each addressing a specific element of knowledge co-creation. WP7 is a transversal work package, integrating the outcome of all WPs for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation processes: it aims to ensure that the recommendations and insights arising from the CIRAN project are visible to a wider audience and can be implemented at a European scale, and may be exploited by players of vulnerable areas outside of the EU.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	3
2	Communication	4
2.1	Key Stakeholders	5
2.2	General Communication Messages.....	6
2.2.1	Key Messages	7
2.3	Communication Activities.....	7
2.4	Challenges for the Communication Strategy.....	9
3	Dissemination	10
3.1	Stakeholders	10
3.2	Dissemination Tools and Activities.....	10
3.3	Challenges for the Dissemination Strategy	11
4	Exploitation.....	12
4.1	Objectives of the Exploitation Plan	12
4.2	CIRAN’s Outputs	12
4.3	Target Groups for the Exploitation.....	12
4.4	Exploitation Strategy in CIRAN	13
4.5	Overview of Exploitation Actions	13
4.5.1	Planned Exploitation Actions.....	13
4.6	Exploitation Challenges	14
5	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	15
6	Timeline of Actions	17
7	Conclusions.....	18
8	Bibliography.....	19
	Annexe 1: Website and Stylebook.....	20

List of Figures

Figure 1 – CIRAN’s Major Stakeholders, according to their power and interest, and corresponding outreach prescriptions. Adapted from Mendelow (1991).....	6
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1 Introduction

The present dissemination and exploitation strategy (D7.1) outlines the approach, objectives, and target groups for the dissemination and exploitation activities to be implemented in the Horizon Europe-funded project “CIRAN – Critical Raw materials extraction in environmentally protected areas”. The main objective of CIRAN is to develop, test, and validate processes to arrive at systemic policymaking, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs). This strategy (further on, also “Plan”) is written against the background of the main project objectives. Its main purpose is to define the scope of communication, dissemination, and exploitation actions to be carried out by the project to facilitate the transfer, uptake, and further use of the recommendations and insights generated.

To begin with, it is worth noting that communication, dissemination, and exploitation are three distinct but related concepts:

- **Communication** refers to providing information and raising awareness towards the project in general, such as the societal challenges and its European added value, by answering basic questions and creating an active engagement strategy with key project stakeholders. In the case of CIRAN, the communication will start and mainly focus on the direct engagement of the citizens of the five selected communities (WP5).
- **Dissemination** actions focus on the contribution to Open Science by the provision of the project’s key stakeholders, who are expected to use the knowledge generated for further actions. The knowledge transfer will occur within planned actions, including presentations at conferences and knowledge-sharing events, peer-reviewed papers, direct exchange with relevant networks, associations, and other groups, including clustering and community-of-practice activities.
- **Exploitation** refers to making recommendations for societal and political purposes. The CIRAN project’s outputs focus on changing attitudes and ensuring openness to other disciplines in the areas of policy design and policy implementation. Hence, exploitation relies on a knowledge transfer strategy set out after identifying exploitable outputs and stakeholders.

In summary, communication covers promoting all aspects of the project mainly, but not exclusively, via direct engagement, while dissemination focuses on the project’s results, and exploitation on the uptake of selected project outputs. Annexed to this document is the CIRAN Stylebook, which defines the project’s visual identity. The following table summarises the key elements of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures planned within the project as set out in the Grant Agreement.

2 Communication

The CIRAN communication and engagement strategy is tightly linked to WP2, WP3, WP5, and WP7 via the engagement of citizens, particularly those in affected areas. In sum, the CIRAN communication and engagement strategy considers:

- The **scoping and discussion methodology**, designed to gradually involve the Expert Groups (EGs), citizen groups, and professionals (that form the community of practice), with a series of targeted activities (e.g., workshops, clustering events, etc) (WP1, WP3, and WP7).
- The **societal data** generated with the help of CIRAN on citizens' viewpoints (WP3 and WP5).
- The work of mapping into socio-political contexts the **narratives of the wider public** debate concerning minerals extraction and nature protection, with a view to better appreciate the various stakeholders' values and concerns (WP3 and WP5).

To achieve this level of engagement with citizens, CIRAN's communication will focus on providing context, basic educational materials and creating a dialogue through the project's online tools. As a result, the project objectives, actions, and benefits can be shared and widely understood, demonstrating the impact and relevance of the project to the stakeholders.

The key elements for maximising CIRAN impact, including the definition of target groups and expected outcomes, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Summary of the CIRAN project key elements for maximising project impact.

Specific Needs Addressed by CIRAN	Expected Results from CIRAN	D&E&C Measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure the supply of CRMs necessary to foster the EU transition towards a green and digital economy. • Protection of Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity and sustainable management of natural resources. • Reduce dependency on primary CRMs imported through low-impact responsible domestic sourcing and processing of CRMs in the EU. • Consensus on long-term management of natural resources, supported by inclusive, transparent and democratic decision-making processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-wide sensitivity maps of potential conflicts over natural resources usage. • Protocol for environmental assessment of CRMs' extraction in environmentally protected areas. • A tested and verified (new) logical framework for policymaking and permitting, based on co-creation and transparent consultation processes with communities on rights, obligations, and governance responsibilities concerning the extraction of CRMs in environmentally protected areas. • A community of practice that supports knowledge exchange, peer training and capacity building related to minerals permitting and environment protection that will remain active after the project funding period. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination to policymakers: Scientific publications of results and presentations in relevant EU events (e.g., Raw Materials Week in Brussels). • Exploitation: alignment of policy design and policy implementation levels concerning the extraction of CRMs in environmentally protected areas across the EU, fostered by a community of practice of professionals from national, regional, and local authorities active in land-use planning, nature conservation, mining and natural resources management. • Communication with citizens: transfer of science-based information in community dialogues and cocreation processes and expansion of discussions, brainstorming and ideation to the general public through online platforms.

Target Groups	Outcomes	Impacts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary target: policymakers and implementers engaged in mineral resources' management, nature conservation, and land-use planning, from national, regional and local authorities of EU MS, and who are indispensable to enable the domestic extraction of CRMs and attain the EU Green Deal climate ambition. Other targets: experts in nature conservation; the technical staff of industries in the extractive sector; people active in economic sectors that thrive in environmentally protected areas; municipalities and inspection agents that enforce regulations; citizens from communities located in environmentally protected areas (and their vicinity); and consumer organisations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policymakers and implementers acquainted with the importance of putting people at the centre of decision-making processes. Authorities inspired to adopt cross-sectoral policies and permitting processes (for the extraction of CRMs in environmentally protected areas) co-developed with communities and that define rights, obligations and governance responsibilities of Estate, the mining companies, and the communities. Citizens more conscious of the uncertainty and the challenges of reducing societal vulnerabilities and the energy transition in the EU, and its repercussions on the systemic management of natural resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic: Supply security of CRMs and reduced economic vulnerabilities, fostering the development of emerging technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the EU digital and green transitions. Societal: Empowered citizens and strengthened and more resilient, inclusive and democratic EU societies, benefiting from high standards of environmental protection. Governance: balanced conservation and rational use of natural resources enabled by systemic permitting procedures, integrated policy design and enhanced management of coupled social–ecological–economic systems.

2.1 Key Stakeholders

CIRAN's primary target group is policy-makers and -implementers engaged in mineral resources management, nature conservation, and land-use planning. This group is indispensable for the success of the project and for the further implementation of the results and exploitation of the knowledge acquired. As previously mentioned, WP2, WP3, WP5, and WP7 include activities to share, use, and communicate the results of CIRAN, aiming to involve three different groups, which make the secondary targets:

- **Expert Groups**, who will offer new perspectives and foster dialogue throughout the project.
- **Citizens from five communities**, who will take part in creating and testing fair and balanced agreements/contracts that link economic, social, and ecological aspects.
- A community of practice (**CIRAN Forum**) that consists of people who work in land-use management (including representatives of national regional and local authorities), minerals extraction, environmental conservation, water protection, geological surveys, and the minerals industry, who will learn from each other and build their skills, and who will continue their collaboration after the project ends.

Further stakeholder groups have also been identified, including the following actors:

- **Experts in nature conservation** (e.g., wildlife biologists, conservation scientists, landscape rehabilitation experts).
- **Technical staff of industries in the extractive sector** (e.g., mining companies, providers of equipment and consumables, consultants).
- **Stakeholders in economic sectors** that thrive in environmentally protected areas (e.g., tourism and recreation, organic farming, ecotourism, beekeeping).

- **Municipalities and inspection agents** that enforce environmental and industrial regulations.
- **Citizens and consumer organisations** (citizens from communities located in environmentally protected areas and their vicinity are a priority within this group).

Figure 1 – CIRAN’s major stakeholders, according to their power and interest, and corresponding outreach prescriptions. Adapted from Mendelow (1991).

CIRAN has been designed through a community-centred approach based on the real experiences and perspectives of different stakeholders who deal with various aspects of economic, societal, and ecological dimensions. This approach generates many opportunities for communication and direct engagement and dissemination that can reach beyond the local level and have an impact at the transnational scale, as well as ensuring the uptake of the CIRAN’s recommendations and insights during and after the funded period.

2.2 General Communication Messages

On a general basis, as part of wider communication, the efforts in CIRAN will reflect answers to the following major questions:

- What is CIRAN about (general overview)?
- What is the aim of CIRAN (specific objectives)?
- What is the potential impact of CIRAN (expected outputs, added value generated, who is impacted)?
- Who is involved in CIRAN (partners and stakeholders)?
- What are the intermediate and final recommendations?
- What are the key milestones of the project (most important goals achieved)?

Most of the communication actions will be developed around these questions, with a schedule depending on the specific development stage of the project. This will ensure that the messages will reach the targeted groups with appropriate timing and content, resulting in reaching the CIRAN objectives to the maximum extent possible.

2.2.1 Key Messages

In addition to the general messages described above, a set of key messages will guide these wider communication efforts. The key messages are set out here:

- 1 CIRAN aims to increase the overall level of sustainability of the EU society by fostering low-risk and low-impact extraction strategies for mineral raw materials.
- 2 CIRAN brings together external expert stakeholders and will advance a community of practice that will remain active after the project.
- 3 CIRAN will involve five European communities in focus groups and public meetings to understand the societal dimensions of the consequences of energy and climate transition in Europe.

The key messages will be further developed and updated based on interim and final project results with the involvement of Consortium Partners during the life of the project.

2.3 Communication Activities

CIRAN's communication strategy is based on active engagement with the stakeholders, establishing an open dialogue through social media, the website, and the CIRAN Forum, and by participating in events and other awareness-raising actions. Communicating efforts will be maximised through already existing networks from project partners. The corresponding graphic identity of CIRAN is annexed to this document.

Specific communication objectives in CIRAN:

- To **inform stakeholders** about the project outputs and results and to seek synergies with related projects.
- To set the stage and **ensure effective dissemination of CIRAN outputs** once they are achieved, and to support the uptake of results by policymakers and -implementers.
- To **create a community of practice** that supports knowledge exchange, peer training, and capacity-building related to minerals permitting and environment protection that will remain active after the funding period.

Our broader objectives concerning communication are:

- To **engage with stakeholders**: obtaining knowledge from stakeholders, providing channels and instruments to receive feedback, and promoting interaction.
- To **raise awareness**: informing the stakeholders concerned and, at a later stage, once lessons have been learned from direct engagement, the wider public about the actions undertaken during the project's lifetime.

As per the European Commission (EC) guidance for science communication for evidence-based policymaking (Šucha & Sienkiewicz, 2020), the main building blocks for effective citizen engagement are: 1) consultation; 2) educational efforts; and 3) tools for participation. This represents the roadmap to follow in CIRAN's communication for the wider public. Consultation is to be carried out through the project's social media activities in the form of online questionnaires and engagement with the comments on the platforms. In addition, following the workshops planned under WP5, educational materials will be created throughout the whole project, informed by the results of such workshops and of the "What if" scenarios in WP3.

The communication strategy will encompass the development of the project image. For this, a logo and general branding colour schemes for the website, social media, and all other uses have been developed. These will provide a clear identity and branding for the project throughout its lifetime. The latter stages of

communication will aim to raise stakeholders' interest and leverage the uptake of project results. The action will utilise partners' existing channels, such as ALDA's podcasts and newsletters.

The tools to facilitate the communication are as follows:

- **Website:** The website will serve as a main repository of information, materials, and outputs of CIRAN. In addition, it will support the project's activities by informing visitors about news, events, workshops, meetings, milestones, and any other information relevant to the communication of the project.
- **Social media:** Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn and Instagram will carry the general communication of the project (and will be used mainly for dissemination after the project end).
- **Brochures, infographics, and factsheets:** A set of materials conveying the general communication messages will be created to address all target groups and will consist of five infographics, ten factsheets, and two digital brochures. Electronic brochures will be distributed in PDF format for wide dissemination and made available on the website for download. The digital factsheets uploaded to the website will be designed with interactive shapes and images. Posters will also be created for conferences and events where CIRAN participates. The language for these materials will be English, with the possibility of translating and adapting them to other languages as needed.
- **Press releases and media kits:** To be issued whenever an important project milestone is reached. This instrument will be used to inform about meetings, workshops, conferences, reached milestones, or any other news regarding the project that can be relevant for the media. Press releases will be uploaded onto the website and distributed to the relevant media. The content of the press release can be translated and adapted to better satisfy the needs for each one of the regions where the Consortium carries out their actions.
- **Video contest and short videos for social media:** A video contest for secondary-school students will address the importance CRMs and safeguarding natural ecosystems. INTRAW and the Expert Groups will facilitate the contact with teachers, and selected members will be part of the jury. The awarded short videos will be uploaded to CIRAN's YouTube channel and used to introduce the CIRAN concept and activities.
- **Animation video:** An animation video with subtitles will explain the project approach and recommendations.
- **CIRAN events:** Will consist of consultation meetings, workshops, and events with the Expert Groups, the CIRAN Forum and citizens from five communities located in or nearby environmentally protected areas. The community actions will consist of, approximately, ten consultation meetings with community representatives and five capacity-building workshops.

2.4 Challenges for the Communication Strategy

To ensure a smooth implementation of the communication strategy, a series of likely challenges and recommended mitigation approaches have been identified, and are listed in the table below.

Table 2 – Challenges to be considered during the implementation of the communication strategy.

Challenge	Explanation	Mitigation
Delays on the Implementation	Due to unforeseen circumstances, or due to the evolving characteristic of the project, some delays on the implementation of the communication actions may emerge.	A timeline is established based on the Gantt Chart of the Grant Agreement. It will guide the implementation of the communication actions. In case a delay occurs, the action should take place as soon as possible, avoiding major delays. If the action is no longer relevant, a similar relevant action should take place.
Conflicting Viewpoints	Due to the nature of CIRAN, it is possible that conflicting viewpoints might appear in the press, social media, and other audiences.	The wording and creation of materials is carefully monitored by the WP leader, SGU, and the Coordinator and agreed upon with the rest of the Consortium. If a conflict arises, Task Leader will inform the WP Leader and the Coordinator to agree on a conflict resolution, depending on the severity of the issue. In cases considered as severe, the issue will be discussed internally, arguments will carefully structured and the public argument flaw will be monitored with the involvement of key project partners.
Interdependency and Cooperation among Work Packages	As emphasised throughout this deliverable, the work of WP7 and, concretely, the communication strategy, is interlinked with and constantly depends on the progress conducted by other WPs.	Keeping track of the project's progress, regularly, overall and by WP, by presenting the most relevant updates at monthly online Consortium Meetings, via email exchanges with the responsible partners for the dedicated tasks, and at in-person meetings.

3 Dissemination

The main objective of this chapter is to provide a framework for effectively disseminating and informing about the outputs of CIRAN to the key project stakeholders.

3.1 Stakeholders

The dissemination focuses its efforts on those demographics that could make use of the results for further actions, namely, policy-makers and -implementers engaged in mineral resources management, nature conservation, and land-use planning, as well as industry actors, from national, regional, and local authorities of the European Member States, who are indispensable to enabling the domestic extraction of CRMs and attain the EU Green Deal climate ambition (*see Chapter 2*).

3.2 Dissemination Tools and Activities

For CIRAN, a wide variety of dissemination channels and tools will be implemented. While striving for the highest possible level of synergy among all the instruments applied, some of them will be tailored to meet the specific needs of certain stakeholders. The list of tools used during the project's dissemination includes:

- **Website:** Specific sub-pages of the CIRAN webpage will be used to detail the outputs of the project and other actions by the Consortium.
- **Social media:** Certain social media channels will disseminate to specific stakeholders:
 - LinkedIn will provide a place (via a LinkedIn group) for the CIRAN Forum.
 - Twitter will address policymakers, authorities, and professional groups.
- **External events:** Presentations, interviews, and presence at mining-related events will create opportunities to engage with stakeholders interested in learning more about the project outputs. Policymakers and implementers, government authorities, and experts in nature conservation and extractive industries will be the target groups for these actions, as they are the ones who can make use of and ensure the uptake of the outputs of the project.
- **Publications:** in peer-reviewed journals, professional magazines, and other news services.
- The creation and dissemination of **informational materials**, such as brochures, videos, and (recorded) webinars to raise awareness about the aims, goals, and outputs of the CIRAN project among stakeholders and the general public by using the website, participation in high-impact events, clustering actions, and other dissemination actions.

3.3 Challenges for the Dissemination Strategy

To ensure a smooth implementation of the dissemination strategy, a series of potential challenges and recommended approaches for their mitigation are outlined in the table below.

Table 3 – Challenges to be considered during the implementation of the dissemination strategy.

Challenge	Explanation	Mitigation
Limited Awareness	There may be limited awareness of the objectives, goals and outputs of the CIRAN project among stakeholders, especially policymakers, which would jeopardise the uptake of its recommendations.	WP7 is designed to raise awareness with the help of the partners. A close monitoring of the effectiveness of the dissemination actions will be carried out by the Coordinator and the WP leader to ensure maximum impact.
Lack of Interest	The project recommendations might face lack of interest from some key stakeholders.	The support of the Expert Group and the constant evaluation and monitoring of the tools, messages and actions used to disseminate the insights and recommendations to the appropriate audience should counteract this. In case this challenge arises, the strategy will be re-assessed within the Consortium.

4 Exploitation

The most relevant uptake of CIRAN results will take place at the policy-design and policy-implementation levels, by exploiting the results of WP6 through the CIRAN Forum. As such, the following plan centres around the CIRAN Forum and the materials and actions that the Forum will create with the aim of encouraging the uptake of the insights and recommendations.

4.1 Objectives of the Exploitation Plan

At this stage of the project, the exploitation plan will serve as a roadmap for the Consortium to foster the eventual uptake of CIRAN's outputs including recommendations and insights from the CIRAN project beyond the funding period.

4.2 CIRAN's Outputs

CIRAN's project main outputs rely mainly on the results of WP6 "Towards efficient policymaking" being fostered by the CIRAN forum. At the time of writing this Deliverable, the main identified outputs are outlined below:

- **CIRAN Policy Recommendations:** the bottom-line output from the project, the conclusions and a roadmap towards a new social model contract defining the rights, obligations, benefits and responsibilities between governments and communities.
- **Logical Framework:** provides a tool to balance interests and objectives while ensuring that society's critical needs and environmental vulnerabilities are reconciled.
- **CIRAN Forum:** a community of practice that will remain active after the funding period supporting the uptake of good practices. The Forum will continue work after the funding period actively sponsored and supported by the coordinator, INTRAW, and it will be instrumental in the uptake and exploitation of project results by national, regional, and local authorities active in land-use planning, nature conservation, mining, and natural resources management across Europe.

Further, non-measurable, but equally important outputs of the CIRAN project to be achieved through the exploitation of the results, include:

- Authorities inspired to **adopt systemic cross-sectoral policies and permitting processes** (for the extraction of CRMs in environmentally protected areas) that reconcile society's need for mineral raw materials with the need to protect our natural environment, its services and biodiversity.
- Citizens becoming **more conscious of the uncertainties and the challenges** of reducing societal vulnerabilities and bringing about the energy transition in the EU, and its repercussions on the systemic management of natural resources.

4.3 Target Groups for the Exploitation

Considering that the outputs of CIRAN are the Policy Recommendations and Logical Frameworks concerning the extraction of CRMs in environmentally protected areas across the EU, the main targets are policymakers and -implementers. CIRAN's Expert Groups and members of the community of practice engaged in project activities will play an essential role in the uptake and exploitation of project results.

4.4 Exploitation Strategy in CIRAN

The most relevant uptake of CIRAN results will take place at the policy design and policy implementation levels, fostered by the CIRAN Forum. It is expected that professionals from across all EU Member States with links to national, regional, and local authorities relevant in the domains of minerals extraction and permitting, land-use planning, and nature protection will subscribe to the CIRAN Forum. To ensure a successful uptake of the results of the project, the exploitation strategy will focus on achieving the following objectives:

- 1) Knowledge transfer of the outputs.
- 2) Stakeholder engagement.
- 3) Creation and maintenance of the CIRAN Forum.

The actions planned in these areas are often complementary or interconnected with other tasks within WP2, WP3, and WP5.

4.5 Overview of Exploitation Actions

The following planned exploitation actions are the first set of baseline activities to take place in the frame of WP3, WP5, and WP7 of the project, which aim at gathering information from which knowledge will be derived (mainly in WP6). Moreover, they aim to facilitate knowledge transfer and stakeholder engagement to maximise the impact of the CIRAN project's outputs.

As previously mentioned, this Plan is to be regularly updated with the information collected through the exploitation actions and the feedback of the Consortium, expert groups and the CIRAN Forum, hence the upcoming list may be expanded throughout the project's lifetime.

4.5.1 Planned Exploitation Actions

The foreseen exploitation actions at project level are outlined below:

- Engaging and informing the participants of the **CIRAN Forum** about the policy recommendations and insights resulting from the project.
- Creation of one Massive Open On-Line Course (**MOOC**), which will be prepared to provide them with the educational tools on the CIRAN outputs and recommendations for implementation in their scope of work.
- **Engagement with policymakers** at the EU and national levels to advocate the adoption of the CIRAN recommendations in policy-design and -implementation processes. Previous partners' experience, the EGs and the CIRAN Forum will allow for a broad contact pool and for the presentation of the project outputs to a large number of policymakers and implementers, who are the main target of CIRAN project's exploitation.
- Development of **training materials** and a MOOC. The MOOC will be designed to capture the attention of young professionals in public administration to the challenges of the European Green Deal, understood as a gateway to further resources.

4.6 Exploitation Challenges

It is anticipated that the consortium may encounter various challenges that could potentially hinder the uptake and implementation of CIRAN’s recommendations during the development of exploitation activities. In order to proactively address these challenges, a set of mitigation measures have been identified. These are outlined in the table below.

Table 4 – Challenges to be considered during the implementation of the exploitation activities.

Challenge	Explanation	Mitigation
Conflicting Interests	There may be conflicting interests among different stakeholders, which could make it challenging to reach a consensus on clear policy recommendations	The work of the EG and the CIRAN Forum should aid to mitigate this challenge, as there will be extensive dialogue in open and safe spaces with representatives of all stakeholder groups.
CIRAN Forum Remaining Active Beyond the Project Period	Keeping the CIRAN Forum active beyond the project period might be challenging due to the lack of dedicated resources of the organization in charge.	Finding extra resources for managing the Forum; Generating content on relevant topics on a regular basis that enhances the engagement of Forum members.

5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To evaluate the performance of the communication and dissemination actions, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were established using a SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound) approach. The KPIs to be used in CIRAN are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 – CIRAN’s Key Performance Indicators.

Dissemination Channel	KPI	Success Indicator	Role of Partners
Project Website (ciranproject.eu)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of hits - Page views - Average time spent - Project material downloaded - Emails/request for information received 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visits to multiple subpages, especially those of results and downloads. - 50 project material downloads/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute actively with materials for the website - Promote the website using the partners’ institutional channels and social media
Social Media: Facebook Twitter Instagram LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of followers/members - Number of likes, shares and comments - Engagement rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Average 500 followers/members by year 2 - More than 100 tweets on Twitter - More than 10 interactions per publication from year 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow CIRAN social media - Share the content published by CIRAN social media - Share useful news and comments on social media groups - Make use of designated hashtags
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of subscribers of CIRAN channel - Number of views per video 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 100 video views per year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subscribe to CIRAN YouTube channel - Disseminate CIRAN YouTube videos when published through the institution channels (ex. share on social media)
Press Releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of press releases produced, translated, downloaded, and distributed - Number of news originating from press releases published on media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Press releases created for relevant milestones about CIRAN - Press releases successfully distributed to the media - News originating from press releases published on media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribute CIRAN press releases through the institutions’ network - Provide information for press releases when requested - Provide translations for press releases when/if needed
Brochures, Infographics,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of items produced, translated, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 infographics published - 10 factsheets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide information for the elaboration of the

Dissemination Channel	KPI	Success Indicator	Role of Partners
Factsheets, and Animation	downloaded, printed, and distributed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 digital brochures - 1 animation video with subtitles in different languages will explain the project approach and policy recommendation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> brochure, infographics, and factsheets - Have the project brochure/related project material at attended/organized events
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of peer reviewed scientific papers - Number of journal publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 20 publications by the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify possible publication opportunities
CIRAN Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of workshops - Number of conferences - Number of attendees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 10 consultation meetings counting with community representatives by the end of the project - Five capacity-building workshops organised by the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support events' organization and promotion at national level
External Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of events attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 15 conferences/ workshops attended by the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify possible external events to be attended by CIRAN - Participate in external events
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of newsletters published - Number of subscribers to the newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biannual newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute actively with materials and information for the newsletter
Video Contest and Short Videos for Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of participants - Number of views for the videos - Interest evaluated through engagement on social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 30 participants - Increased visits to the website, social media, and YouTube pages during the contest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - INTRAW and the EGs will facilitate the contact with teachers, and selected members will be part of the jury - Support in promotion

6 Timeline of Actions

The following table shows an approximation for the timing of the actions for communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the project, envisioned in the Grant Agreement. Depending on the implementation of the actions and on any challenge that might come up, the timing might be altered. Updates of the deliverable will reflect the adjusted timing agreed by the Consortium.

Table 6 – CIRAN's communication and dissemination timeline.

M01	M02	M03	M04	M05	M06	M07	M08	M09	M10	M11	M12
Social Media Campaign	Update of social media	Social Media Campaign	Launch of the website v1	Electronic brochure	Deliverable 7.1	Social Media Campaign		Animated video	Website v2	Social Media Campaign	
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign	Update of Deliverable 7.1	Social Media Campaign	Electronic brochure	Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign	
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign		Social Media Campaign		CIRAN Conference in Brussels	Social Media Campaign

7 Conclusions

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan for CIRAN establishes a framework for communicating and engaging with the main target groups, keeping the wider audience informed, and for the effective promotion and dissemination of the project outputs to different stakeholders who are interested in or affected by the project. It also gives guidelines to adapt the communication and dissemination efforts to the needs of each stakeholder group to maximise impact. Moreover, it provides a structure to be followed and a common outreach strategy for all partners that uses a consistent identity that is reflected through all the activities and materials. At the same time, it defines partners' responsibilities and expected contributions to the dissemination of CIRAN.

The application of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will increase the visibility of the project, ensuring that the CIRAN recommendations and insights are well disseminated to and uptaken by relevant stakeholders. The possible emerging risks and challenges of its implementation have been analysed and corresponding mitigation approaches were outlined. The Plan will be continuously monitored, adapted, and updated throughout the project implementation, as new findings and outcomes emerge. Additionally, formal reviews of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will take place at M18 and M36 to assess its effectiveness and make any necessary adjustments based on the project's progress.

8 Bibliography

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Annexe 1: Website and Stylebook

1. Website

The website for the CIRAN project (<https://ciranproject.eu>) will serve as the central online communication channel. Along with a description of the project and its objectives, the website will include all relevant news from CIRAN and its Consortium, as well as information regarding events attended. Furthermore, it will include a sign-up form for the bi-annual newsletter that will be produced, summarizing all the news, information, opportunities, and milestones achieved by the project during its lifetime.

The website will be developed at different stages as the project progresses: in the first stage, general information about the project, its goals, and the Consortium will be presented. During the following stages, information about CIRAN developments will be gradually added in the form of new sections.

Figure 1 – Overview of CIRAN’s Website (ciranproject.eu).

1.1 Stage 1

The first version of the website will have the following structure:

- Main page (Home), encompassing the following contents:
 - The CIRAN Project: Short description about the project in the header.
 - Informative section: presented in a section divided in three parts, each one with a descriptive picture, providing information about:
 - What will CIRAN achieve?
 - Why is it important?
 - How will CIRAN achieve its objectives?
 - Long lasting effects of CIRAN: section with information regarding the three expected outputs for CIRAN.
 - News section: relevant news produced by CIRAN.
 - Newsletter sign up form: users will be able to directly sign up to the CIRAN newsletter from the main page.
 - Consortium: logos from the Consortium members.
- News & Events
- Consortium: logos and names from the Consortium members.
- Press: repository for press releases, media kit, press contact info.

Figure 2 – CIRAN website stage 1 internal structure.

1.2. Stage 2

During the second stage of the website development, the structure will encompass the following contents:

- Main page (Home), containing the contents outlined below:
 - The CIRAN Project: Short description about the project in the header.
 - Informative section: presented in a section divided in three parts, each one with a descriptive picture, providing information about:
 - (1) What will CIRAN achieve?;
 - (2) Why is it important?; and
 - (3) How will CIRAN achieve its objectives?
 - Long lasting effects of CIRAN: section with information regarding the three expected outputs for CIRAN.
 - News section: relevant news produced by CIRAN.
 - Newsletter sign up form: users will be able to directly sign up to CIRAN newsletter from the main page.
 - Consortium: logos from the Consortium members.
- CIRAN approach:
 - CIRAN scenarios;
 - CIRAN Case studies;
 - the CIRAN Forum
- Working with communities: Co-creating policy recommendations with civil society
- Educational materials
- Press: repository for press releases, media kit, press contact info.
- Consortium: logos and names from the Consortium members.

Figure 3 – CIRAN website stage 2 internal structure.

2. Project logo

2.1 General Rules

All project material turned public must display the CIRAN logo, at least, in its front page. This includes not only actual project promotion materials, but also event invitations, presentations, or agendas. All possible logo versions for CIRAN are exemplified in this stylebook. They are available online for use and download in the project's SharePoint, under "Repository - Communication - Logo". The version name and information will be clearly stated, so that no mistakes are made.

Importantly, the CIRAN logo must be readable. Minimum and maximum sizes are, however, not established explicitly for dissemination.

2.2 Logo Versions

Table 1 – Versions of CIRAN logo.

Image	Version	Use
	Version 1: CIRAN logo with transparent background.	Used in all coloured web or printed materials, deliverables, or publications.
	Version 2: CIRAN logo, black version.	Used in non-coloured printed materials.
	Version 3: CIRAN logo, white version.	Used in non-coloured printed materials.

3. Rules for Logo Application

3.1 Background

The coloured versions of the logo shall be used mainly on a white, black, or light-coloured background.

If used on a brown/green background (not recommended), use logo version 3.

In case the logo is used on a coloured background, there must be enough contrast between the background and the logo colours – choose the version according to the best option.

The background image shall not have too many details.

3.2 Positioning

The logo shall be placed at a central and visible position.

The logo shall be placed in the outside or front cover of any kind of printable material. Otherwise (i.e. electronic dissemination) the logo shall appear as one of the first items and should excel from other elements.

3.3 Minimum Distance

In accordance with accessibility terms, in order to be effective and readable, the CIRAN logo needs some space around it – do not use the logo right next to a margin.

3.4 Proportions

If used with other logos (EU emblem, partners' logos), the CIRAN logo shall be at least as big as the other logos and must never be smaller.

3.5 Logo Modification

All logos have been defined and created as a specific artwork and shall not, in any circumstances, be modified besides size without the explicit permission of the WP leader (WP7/Ronald Arvidsson).

Therefore:

- The colours of the logo shall not be changed, and colours must be followed as displayed in Chapter 3.
- No new elements shall be added to the logo, whichever they are.
- The logo shall not be used on coloured backgrounds, if those do not provide sufficient contrast to the logo colour, even if versions 2 or 3 are being used –if this occurs, the background should be changed.
- The logo shall not be cropped, rotated, or distorted.

4. Colour Palette

CIRAN has standards for reproducing colours so that they will always look consistent, no matter where they appear (of course slight variations can occasionally occur). The colours defined here serve as the source for our standard colour palette and should be employed throughout all communications. The colours chosen are the ones from the logos as seen in Chapter 2. The chosen colours are to be used in any type of text that needs highlighting, titles, or headlines.

Three groups of colour codes are provided for different material approaches:

- CMYK (full colour printing)
- RGB (desktop publishing, such as Word or PowerPoint)
- Hexadecimal (web publications; can as well use RGB)

Table 2 – CIRAN colour palette.

	CMYK	Hexadecimal	Colour Example
Green	38, 24, 56, 1	#a4aa81	
Light Brown	11, 58, 81, 1	#dd8046	
Dark Brown	47, 56, 61, 24	#786055	
Gray	43, 42, 38, 3	#968b8c	

5. Typography

Typography is one of the most important design elements when communicating. It is used to clearly separate sections of information, such as headlines, text, or captions, which help the message getting disseminated. The best use of serif fonts (small lines attached to the end of a stroke in a letter or symbol) and sans-serif fonts (do not have the small lines at the end of a letter or symbol) can be reached, depending on what type of communication is being used. For that, a set of rules have been defined.

5.1 When To Use A Specific Font Type

As a rule of thumb, when using Serif fonts in body text (and captions as well), use Sans-Serif fonts for headlines and titles. Otherwise, if using Sans-Serif fonts in body text (and captions as well), use Serif fonts for headlines and titles.

Table 3 – CIRAN font types, by type of material.

Type of material	Body font type
Web material (Websites, other content)	Calibri
Visual Presentations (e.g. poster, presentations)	Poppins
Reports	Calibri

5.2 When To Use A Specific Font Style

Table 4 – CIRAN Font Styles and When to Use Them.

Font style	When to use
Regular	Body text
<i>Italic</i>	Not used
Bold	Titles/headlines

5.3 Text Alignment

Three types of text alignment should be used throughout CIRAN communications depending on the case:

- For documents that contain large text, such as reports, the justify alignment option should be used.
- For text in small columns/spaces (e.g., tables), the left alignment shall be selected.
- Centre alignment may be selected for text inside tables or graphs.

Be careful when using the “justify” alignment as it can alter text disposition and one or more lines of text may appear with unwanted spaces between words.

6. Images

Images are essential for a good dissemination and/or communication effort and need to be chosen carefully.

They must comply, when possible, with the following rules:

- Use images that are related to CIRAN.
- Use images that are in focus.
- Include photo credits and captions, whenever needed.
- In case of using stock photos:
 - Make sure that the photos are open source and credit them when necessary.
 - In case the photos are paid, the license shall be obtained to use them.

7. Linguistic Conventions

The project name, CIRAN, must always be presented in capital letters, unless it is otherwise impossible (e.g., Facebook profile page). It shall not have any other kind of characters around it (e.g., “ ”). For all linguistic conventions, the *English Style Guide* of the European Commission shall be consulted and referred to: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-03/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf

8. Information on EU Funding

8.1 Use of the EU Emblem

Unless otherwise agreed upon with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies, or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., logos of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Funded by the
European Union

The EU emblem can be found in CIRAN SharePoint (Repository - Communication - EU Emblem).

8.2 Disclaimer Excluding Commission Responsibility

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

9. Contact Points

For any additional information and assistance related to graphic design and layout configuration of the CIRAN project, you may contact LPRC contact points responsible for this Deliverable, or may refer to any of the contacts provided below:

CIRAN Project Coordinator

International Raw Materials Observatory (INTRAW) / Brussels / <https://inraw.eu>

Contact: Vitor Correia (Secretary General), <vcorreia@inraw.eu>.

Work Package 7 (WP7) Leader

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